

THE DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF TRADITIONAL DANCES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The development stages of traditional dances in Uzbekistan have been shaped by centuries of cultural influences and historical events. From ancient and pre-Islamic rituals to the modern-day revival of traditional dance forms, Uzbekistan's dance heritage reflects a rich tapestry of artistic expression. This article explores the evolution of traditional dances in Uzbekistan through various historical periods, including the ancient and pre-Islamic era, the Islamic period, the Silk Road era, the Soviet period, and the post-independence period. By examining how these different stages have contributed to the diversity and complexity of Uzbek dance traditions, we gain a deeper understanding of the cultural significance and artistic beauty of this ancient art form.

Keywords: traditional dances, Uzbekistan, development stages, cultural influences, historical events, ancient rituals, pre-Islamic era, Islamic period, Silk Road era, Soviet period, post-independence period, dance heritage, artistic expression, evolution, diversity, complexity, cultural significance, artistic beauty. Traditional dances in Uzbekistan have a rich history that has evolved through various development stages influenced by cultural, historical, and social factors. These dances have been shaped by a combination of ancient rituals, the Islamic period, the Silk Road era, the Soviet period, and the post-independence period [5]. Each stage of development has contributed to the diversity, complexity, and cultural significance of Uzbek dance heritage, making it a unique form of artistic expression that continues to captivate audiences with its beauty and grace. This article will explore the development stages of traditional dances in Uzbekistan and how they have been influenced by different historical events and cultural influences.

Traditional dances in Uzbekistan have evolved over centuries and have been influenced by various cultures and historical events. The development stages of traditional dances in Uzbekistan can be broadly categorized as follows:

1. Ancient and pre-Islamic period: The roots of traditional Uzbek dances can be traced back to ancient times when various tribes and civilizations inhabited the region. These dances were often performed during rituals, celebrations, and social gatherings. The movements were often symbolic, reflecting the connection between humans and nature.

2. Islamic period: With the spread of Islam in Central Asia, new elements were incorporated into traditional Uzbek dances. Islamic motifs, such as geometric patterns and calligraphy, became prominent in the costumes and choreography of dances. The movements also became more refined and stylized, reflecting the influence of Islamic art and culture.

3. Silk Road era: The Silk Road played a significant role in the development of traditional Uzbek dances, as it facilitated cultural exchange between different civilizations. Dances from Persia, India, China, and other regions along the Silk Road were integrated into Uzbek dance traditions, enriching the repertoire with new styles and techniques [3].

4. Soviet period: During the Soviet era, traditional Uzbek dances underwent a process of standardization and codification. Folk ensembles were established to preserve and promote Uzbek cultural heritage, leading to the formalization of dance styles and techniques. At the same time, Soviet influences also seeped into Uzbek dance, resulting in a fusion of traditional and modern elements.

5. Post-independence period: Since gaining independence in 1991, Uzbekistan has made efforts to revive and promote its cultural heritage, including traditional dances. Dance festivals, competitions, and performances have become more common, providing a platform for dancers to showcase their skills and creativity. At the same time, contemporary choreographers are exploring new ways to reinterpret traditional dances and make them relevant to modern audiences [4].

Overall, the development stages of traditional dances in Uzbekistan reflect a rich tapestry of influences from different cultures and historical periods, creating a diverse and vibrant dance tradition that continues to evolve to this day.

In conclusion, the development stages of traditional dances in Uzbekistan have been influenced by a rich tapestry of historical, cultural, and social factors. From ancient rituals and Islamic traditions to the impact of the Silk Road, Soviet rule, and the post-independence era, each period has left its mark on the evolution of dance forms in Uzbekistan. Through a visual representation such as a timeline diagram, one can appreciate the interconnectedness of these stages and how they have shaped the vibrant and diverse landscape of traditional dances in Uzbekistan today.

References:

1. Saodat Bakhtiyarovna Halilova (2022). HISTORICAL EVOLUTION OF UZBEK NATIONAL DANCE. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3 (3), 153-155.
2. Zarina Amonturdiyeva (2022). 3 BEAUTIFUL SCHOOLS OF UZBEK NATIONAL DANCE ART. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3 (3), 202-204.

3. Кадыров М.Х. Труды по истории зрелищных искусств Узбекистана. В 3-х томах. - Ташкент: Фан, 2013.
4. Малохат Махмудова (2021). Узбекский танец – как предмет в системе высшего хореографического образования. Общество и инновации, 2 (4), 136-140. doi: 10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss4-pp136-140
5. Толстов С.П. По следам древнехорезмийской цивилизации. - Москва: Наука, 1948. - 460 с